

Why is daylight saving time dying hard? The hearing at the US Senate shows

José María Martín-Olalla[✉]

*Universidad de Sevilla[✉], Facultad de Física, Departamento de Física de la Materia Condensada, ES41012 Sevilla, Spain**

Jorge Mira[✉]

*Universidade de Santiago de Compostela[✉], Facultade de Física,
Departamento de Física Aplicada and iMATUS, ES15782 Santiago de Compostela, Spain[†]*

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We offer a review of the recent hearing at the US Senate on seasonal daylight saving time with an examination of the central arguments surrounding seasonal time policy. Essentially the two main witnesses —Dr. Karin Johnson and Jay Karen— expressed their abhorrence for one of the choices —either permanent standard time (Karen), or permanent daylight saving time (Johnson)—. Irrespective of how annoying or complex clock regulations might be, this opposing interests —which stratify socially and geographically— highlight the role of seasonal clocks as a meaningful, functional compromise.

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On April 10, 2025 the US Senate held a hearing on whether to keep daylight saving time (DST).¹ We offer here a critical review of the hearing in relation with the groundings of seasonal clocks and their role in aligning human activity with sunrise. We leave to the reader to decide whether the following is an eulogy of the practice, or a description of why it is dying hard.

The chairman of the hearing, senator Cruz (Texas), presented the biannual changing of the clocks as an annoying, antiquated ritual with negligible benefits, and with hazardous by-effects in the form of increased accidents and strokes around transition dates. His speech was followed by senator Rochester (Delaware), who concurred with Cruz. The first witness, Scott Yates, a lobbyist from the Lock the Clock Movement,² also agreed with Cruz and Rochester. Yates sees the seasonal time as a “relic” and did not provide a single rationale behind its practice, which, apparently, is an unpractical, unnecessary complexity that can only be associated with increased hazards. For Yates the seasonal times exists today just due to the inability to choose which time should

survive. Why are the seasonal clocks so difficult to cancel? The hearing provided a few hints.

Dr. Karin Johnson, a witness speaking on behalf of the American Academy of Sleep Medicine (AASM), sustained that “the spring clock change to daylight saving time is bad, but permanent daylight savings time is worse.” There are some good arguments with this view.[1, 2] The biannual changing of the clocks brings a few short-living hazards related to the human body adaptation to the new setting, whereas permanent DST may bring sustained hazards during the months of winter in the form of dark start times for increasing shares of population, including scholars, which people tend to abhor. We note that for Dr. Johnson the current policy is the lesser of two evils, with permanent DST being no-go choice.

Jay Karen was a witness speaking in the name of the National Golf Course Owners Association, and representing, broadly speaking, the point of view of the recreational sector. It should be noted that the recreational sector largely originated and experienced dramatic growth throughout the 20th century. Thus it has mainly existed under the rules of seasonal time only and, therefore, is sensitive to their canceling. Karen maintained a balanced position which, to us, did not seem too hard against the current practice, preferred by 27% of the owners, a staggering high number given the mainstream. In short Karen just urged “the Senate to avoid the consequences of permanent standard time [ST].” To

* olalla@us.es

† jorge.mira@usc.es

¹ <https://www.c-span.org/program/senate-committee/senate-hearing-on-daylight-saving-time-versus-standard-time> 658386

² <https://locktheclock.net/>

this sector of activity, prone to seasonal variations, this is the no-go choice.

To understand Karen's point of view, we must get back to how some sleep doctors and some physiologists, including Dr. Johnson, describe the interaction of the seasonal cycle of light and dark with human activity. Morning light is key for human body clock, they say, therefore people should start their day in daylight; this is good for human circadian rhythms and human body, and explains why permanent DST is often abhorred. In summer earlier sunrises will make people to wake up earlier, ideally without requiring an alarm clock; without the changing of the clock the start of the day would swiftly come after a stand-by period.[3]

The stand-by period is the origin of the "waste" of daylight that gave birth to the "saving" of daylight in early 20th century.[4] It had been described by Hudson in 1895[5] who just proposed the following: make use of your early summer awakening to start your day earlier, and then enjoy an extra-hour daylight in your recreational time. This, and not energy saving, is the core of the seasonal time.[6] Buried among the many hazards specifically associated with seasonal clocks are two simple questions: what is wrong, on an individual basis, with that behavior? If individuals can adapt to waking up and start working in winter, what factors might discourage a similar adjustment in summer?

Hudson's proposal can be described as "duty first, then pleasure", whereas the AASM is saying: "a bit of pleasure, then duty, then more pleasure". Broadly speaking, many Western modern societies, chiefly the US and the UK, found benefits in the unsegmented recreational time: golfers can hardly get to the course, play a few holes in the summer morning, jump to their working routine and, in the afternoon, get back to the course and complete the round. Here "golf" is used as an educational example only: the same goes with other recreations like hiking, used by Dr. Johnson in the hearing. Eventually, the seasonal time aligned working schedules with sunrise, which is good for human bodies, and optimized the recreational time in a simplistic, coordinated, synchronized way, which is also good for human bodies.[7, 8] In summary, the current seasonal time operates as a compromise between the abhorrence to start the day in the dark hours of the winter morning and the propensity to harvest the summer day the most; in the hearing, only Karen rightfully described the current regulation as a trade-off.

Much of the discussion in the hearing was related to geography. The US is sensitive to the two parameters that matter in this discussion. One is latitude, which is easily addressed: seasonal time is designed for latitudes above some 30 degrees, where the seasonal variation of sunrise time is two hours and the one-hour change makes an impact. Hawaii is not in this range, which explains why seasonal time is not used there. The same issue explains why Mexico recently abandoned the policy. It also applies in Florida: in Miami the sunrise changes

90 minutes only and a seasonal time is less necessary. Thus, it was no surprise to us that senator Scott (Florida) presented an argument against the seasonal time.

The role of longitude requires a detailed explanation. We have presented seasonal time as a compromise between the optimization of the recreational time and the propensity to start the day in daylight. This operates at an individual level. Furthermore, the compromise also operates at social level between early and late risers on a given location, say a person starting the day at 8am and their spouse or neighbor doing so at 9am. The current practice make early risers not too early in winter (should permanent DST be adopted), avoiding dark, cold hours; and make late risers not too late in summer (should permanent ST be adopted), harvesting bright, fresh hours. Finally, the compromise also applies globally within a time zone, which connects with longitude. A person starting at 8am in Boston is a "late riser" compared to a person starting at 8am in Detroit (which is an "early riser"), because the sun rises later in the former city. The seasonal time prevents the Eastern edge of a time zone from being too late in summer, and the Western edge of a time zone from being too early in winter. Permanent ST is usually less appealing in the Eastern edge, while permanent DST is less appealing in the Western edge. However, this problem is often described in a different way: cancelling the seasonal clocks ends up in the sun rising in Boston at 4am in summer, or rising in Detroit at 9am in winter. This five-hour range between two extreme cases tends to make the decision politically impractical and contributes to why seasonal time is dying hard.

The downside of the compromise brought by the time policy are the effects associated with transition dates. However the many research studies that report increased risks associated with transition dates seldom consider the context of the seasonal clocks. Much like in the hearing, no rationale behind them is presented. Specifically they are not described as a natural adaptation to a perennial stimulus. Furthermore, it is seldom emphasized that the size of risks is very very slight compared to the confounding factors associated with the specific issue under study.[9] As an example Fritz et al.[10] studied 21 years of fatal vehicle accidents in the US and reported an increase of the risks of 6% associated with the spring transition. But, the relative standard deviation of their record, which is related to the confounding factors, was 15%. The size of the increase attributed to the changing of the clocks is only 1/3 of the impact of the confounding factors.

Thus, modern statistical methods and big database allow the identification of very slight systematic effects. This is extremely important for the understanding on how small changes in patterns of behavior impact human circadian rhythms, but less significant to sustain a policy. Senator Curtis (Utah) asked whether persons traveling across one time zone "would be subject to those same problems" [of the clock changing]. Dr. Johnson did not

give much importance to traveling (“we adjust to that [the new time] within a day or two”), whereas with the clock policy “we are changing the clock time but we’re not changing the sun”. This is a common misunderstanding among physiologists (see for instance Ref. [11]). Actually, in the seasonal time policy the spring change arrives only after the sun has *changed*, enlarging the morning light by more than one hour, compared to the winter morning light. The individual is just resetting their rhythm to the current, advanced sunrises. Thus, traveling across a time zone and the seasonal clocks bring similar hazards. While traveling across time zones purely for leisure is not advisable, and neither is changing clocks arbitrarily, the seasonal time policy does, in fact, follow a rationale rooted on physiology: maintaining alignment with the sunrise because morning light is key for human body. Eventually, the population-level evidence extracted from the clock changing is showing that the impact of traveling one time zone exists but it is not alarming.

Yates described the seasonal time as a “complexity”, likely because it requires actions from decision-makers, and from the citizens. However, people is less aware that the seasonal time is also a big simplification: preset schedules are functional year-round. In other words, the seasonal policy eases the necessity of “seasonal schedules”, which would be another complexity of their own. Furthermore with seasonal time children and parents, teachers and pupils, commuters and passengers, dealers and customers, early risers and late risers—all of them operating under preset schedules— stay in sync

year-round. The lack of seasonal schedules is an every day evidence saying that the alternating clock has proven functional.[12] Neither permanent ST nor permanent DST proved functional in the past, due to late summer starting schedules (ST) and early winter starting schedules (DST). As a final remark, there is little literature on whether start times have significantly advanced/delayed in the past decades, which would give a hint on whether permanent DST/ST might sustain.

In her initial speech senator Rochester said “we need to find a solution and stick with it.” Respectfully, what if the problem was already addressed and the sticky solution is the one-hundred-year current regulation? What if, instead of finding a solution, the current efforts point towards breaking a meaningful compromise that has proven much annoying but, also, much functional? We end our analysis with a takeaway: we may lock the clock, but we cannot lock the seasons.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors contributed equally to this work.

DECLARATION OF INTEREST

The authors declare no competing interest.

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TIME LINE

We learned of the hearing by an email sent to us by Leonardo Pini, journalist at Northwestern University, see [doi:10.5281/zenodo.15212726](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15212726). We attended live the hearing and then we were able to review it. Eventually, we decided to have our say on it.